

NFDI-MatWerk/IUC02 Definition for Reference Data of Materials Version 1.0 (June 2024)

Reference data of materials

- are documented according to certain standards as well as
- are curated (i.e., generated, maintained, preserved, validated) according to certain standards
- are quantitative data sets (i.e., data + their corresponding metadata)
- have been measured or simulated to a particularly high standard, and
- are generated for a material that has either experienced a well-documented process or is reference material or its composition and structure has been completely characterized.

Reference data of materials can also be derived data from reference data.

These data are distributed with a license (e.g., GPL).

The here addressed standards for documentation, curation and measurement need to be defined for specific materials characteristics (e.g., creep tests) in terms of domain standards. These domain standards are the result of a steered community process.

Standards should integrate as much as possible existing standards (e.g., the individual MatWerk domain standards should be as much as possible consistent).

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